

I-VIDEO IN BASIC PHOTOGRAPHY COURSE FOR SPECIAL EDUCATION NEEDS

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Abstract

The Ministry of Education in Malaysia believes that everyone deserves a chance in education. Because of this belief, the Department of Community College Education has launched various programs for special needs students. Paya Besar Community College (KKPB) had been chosen among others to run a Certificate in Basic Photography (KFI) program starting from July 2013. The special needs students that are expected to enroll in this course are students with learning disabilities. Learning disabilities are neurologically-based processing problems that can interfere with learning basic skills. These conditions must be clinically diagnosed and validated by medical experts. Most of PBCC special needs students have problems focusing, remembering and processing information. These students also have trouble associating their existing knowledge with new knowledge as well as applying it in their learning environment. The I-video is design to assist in the learning and teaching process for this program. The I-video was developed using the Adobe Premiere Pro CS4 with the combination of the blue screen effect technology and suing a studio concept. This innovation applies multimedia interactions that can appeal to special needs students thus completing the learning and teaching proses. The outcome of the I-video has shown an increase in the learning and teaching proses. The concept of this I-video has high potential to be used throughout the Education institution in Malaysia.

Keywords: i-Video, Basic photography, Special education

Introduction

Kolej Komuniti Paya Besar (KKPB) was established on March 1st 2003 under the Malaysian Ministry of Education but due to it not having its own establishment KKPB had to operate at a school which is Seri Damai Secondary School, Kuantan. The first intake was done on 16th July 2003 which involved 40 students enrolling in the Information Technology Certificate and Creative Multimedia (Advertising) Certificate.

On July 1st 2006, KKPB was moved to a permanent campus at Gambang, Pahang. In 2008, KKPB offered a Diploma program in Advertising Technology to students that had completed their Creative Multimedia Certificate. This program which focused on workBased Learning had received cooperation from the industry and Government Linked Companies (GLC).

Now, after 10 years since its establishment, 749 students had graduated from KKPB. 4 other courses had been added which is Certificate in Computer Software Application, Certificate in Creative Multimedia (Advertising), Certificate in Electrical Installation, Certificate in Computer System Support and Certificate in Basic Photography for special needs students.

Overview of the Innovation

In the year 2013, the College Community Education Department (JPKK) under the Ministry of Education (KPM) had launched programs for Special Needs (Learning Disabilities). KKPB was chosen along with other community college to run the Certificate in Basic Photography (KFI) starting July 2013. According to KPM, these programs are focused on student with learning Disabilities. Students who has problems focusing, remembering and processing information are encouraged to apply. Candidates that had been chosen are ask to attend an interview before they are accepted to this program.

Because of their learning disabilities the i-Video was developed as an innovation to assist in the learning and teaching process. Using the Adobe Premiere Pro CS4 software, this innovation applies multimedia interaction using the blue screen effect technology and studio concept. This approach appeals more to special needs students thus making the learning and teaching process more engaging. Since this program had been running, the outcome of the use of the i-Video has shown significant increase in learning and teaching process.

Problem Statement

During the learning and teaching process of the Basic Photography course, lecturers had encountered problems with the students with learning disabilities. Because of this problem, an innovation group was formed and further analysis had been made. The main purpose of this innovation as well as the users of the i-Video was further analyzed so that the objective can be achieved. From the analysis, the students had difficulties remembering the topics that were taught. The lecturers also had problems since it consumes time and energy to repeat the topics 5 to 10 times to ensure the students understand. And what is more important is that these students are able to understand and apply the topics that they learned.

This problem is relevant to their inability to memorize and lack of focus. During the learning process, the students are exposed to many activities. For example, they are taught on how to use YouTube as a method to learn Photography. Upon observation, these students are more focused and showed a lot of interest while watching the videos on YouTube. Because of this observation we've had decided to develop the i-Video to assist in our learning and teaching process.

Objective of the Innovation

Increase the effectiveness of the learning and teaching process for the special needs student of the Basic of Photography program.

Increase the capability of the special needs students to understand and remember what they had learned in class.

To ensure at least 90% of the curriculum objectives are achieved.

To attract the students' attention and maintain their focus during their learning session.

To save time and ease the lecturers teaching special needs students.

Function of the Innovation

Teaching aid in class.

To make the learning and teaching process more interesting and effective.

Revision material for the students that can be used anytime and anywhere after class.

Used as a guide for new lecturers for new intakes.

Lecturers don't need to repeat the lesson thus saving time during the learning and teaching process.

Implementation Period

The i-Video had been fully utilized starting January 2014 until now by the special needs students with learning disabilities at Kolej Komuniti Paya Besar. The i-Video had been through various processes before it can be applied to the students. Starting October 2013, our group had conducted a research on the real problem that occurs in class during the learning and teaching process. After the research had been done, syllabus selection and information accumulated throughout the process are analyzed to accommodate the need of the Basic Photography students. Our group took 2 month starting from November until December 2013 to analyze the appropriate layout design, script, storyboard and the recording hardware needed. The recording process and the video modification took 2 weeks to complete. On January 2014, the i-Video was fully completed and was used by the Basic Photography students of Kolej Komuniti Paya Besar.

Benefits of the Innovation

There are a few benefits that had been identified to ensure the quality of the service provided for our clients. The descriptions and benefits are supported with proof attached.

Creativity

This innovation was fully developed by the Kolej Komuniti Paya Besar innovation group which comprises of 3 lecturers. The use of videos in the learning and teaching process has never been applied before at the college. The concept and idea of this video was found by internet research. However, this video was developed specifically to accommodate the special needs student of the Basic Photography course. Furthermore, the idea and concept of this video is the first innovation that had been developed and applied for special needs students specifically for learning disability students in Community College level throughout Malaysia. (Refer to Table 1).

For learning disability students, distractions during their learning session is a serious matter because they lose focus easily and tend to be distracted by their surroundings. Therefore, the suitable concept of this video is the studio concept. The studio concept is

more appealing and more effective because it has no noise distraction, clearer audio, interactive multimedia application and uses graphics and images that are more clear and vibrant compared to the surroundings of the classroom. The i-Video also uses the *blue screen effect* which makes the video more stimulating. Figure 1 below shows the *blue effect* method used with the Adobe Premier Pro software.

Figure 1 - The blue screen effect method

Level of Implementation

The i-Video had been fully used starting from January 2014 until now by the special needs students at the Kolej Komuniti Paya Besar. Besides that, the i-Video had been contributed to 11 secondary schools in Kuantan for the purpose of exposure to the special education students at the schools.

Replicability

The i-Video can be implemented directly at various locations and there is no need of any modification because it is acceptable at any levels. The contributions to 11 schools throughout Kuantan not only exposed the students to photography but also introduce photography as an interesting choice of career for them.

Efficiency

The development of this video does not involve any cost because the equipment used as well as the skills needed was available at the college. The students showed a lot of interest during class when using the i-Video. Because of their interest and focus during class, there had been a significant increase in their work. Their understanding of the topics taught in class also showed an increase. (Refer to students' work in Figure 2)

The lecturers teaching the students had saved an amount of time explaining to students because they don't need to repeat it numerous times. The i-Video is easy to use because it only requires a computer and can be accessed using a pen drive, CDROM or YouTube.

Significance

The i-Video has given a positive impact to the Malaysian Ministry of Education specifically to the special needs student at Kolej Komuniti Paya Besar. Besides the Malaysian Ministry of Education, the i-Video can also be used by other departments such as the National Autism Center that was established by the Malaysian Prime Minister, Datuk Seri Najib Tun Razak. This is an effective way to introduce photography as a potential career choice.

Figure 2 - Flowchart Process

Findings and Discussion

In the first process of the observation, students are being shown the i-Video. During the entire screening the students showed a lot of interest and are focused to the video. From the observation it is clear that the i-Video is capable of capturing the interest of the students and ensuring that they stay focus throughout the video until it is finished.

The picture shown below (Figure 2) shows students watching the video and answering the questions asked verbally. The students showed a good response after watching the i-Video. The lecturer didn't have to teach repeatedly because the students have watched the video directly from the computer in the classroom using a CDROM or through YouTube.

Figure 3 - Students watching and answering questions verbally

In the second process, the students are tested with more questions to test their understanding after the video is over. The student showed a positive response and was able to answer the questions given.

Figure 4 - Students' reaction after watching the i-Video

In the third process, the students are asked to do practical assignments according to the topic shown in the i-Video. The students' works are evaluated and the findings are the students understand and were able to master the topic that they had learned.

Figure 5 - Students doing their practical.

Figure 6 - Students' works

In the last process, the students are then interviewed to know their feedbacks on the learning and teaching process using the i-Video. The feedbacks that we received were the students are very interested in using the i-Video in their learning process.

The evaluation data that we have received shows an increase in item 1 that is interest and enjoyment when watching the video. As for item 5, there is also an increase which is their understanding while answering questions after watching the video.

Figure 7 - Analysis results of Before and After watching the i-Video

Suggestion and Conclusion

The i-Video project is the first ever developed under the Engineering and Skills Department of Paya Besar Community College with the cooperation of the lecturers from the Advertising Multimedia Unit and General Education Unit.

Using the *blue screen effect* technique and Adobe Pro Premiere, the i-Video was developed to increase the interest as well the understanding of the special needs student specifically learning disabled students.

The production of the first i-Video of LA 1 (Module 1 – Introduction to Photography) Certificate of Basic Photography is the first step for the innovation group in producing the complete video for four other LAs (Modul 1) of this course. With the completion of the videos for this course, the students will witness a reformation of the learning and teaching process.

Hopefully the production and utilization of the i-Video will expand throughout the community college and other institutions making the learning and teaching process more interactive and exciting.

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